

PROVIDING PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL SUPPORT TO FAMILIES
WITH DISABLED CHILDREN

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Abstract. *This study provides information on the provision of pedagogical and psychological support to families with disabled children. The main part of this information is about the support provided by our state to families with disabled children. Also, our study provides information on the psychological health of children with disabilities, children with limited opportunities, and the main aspects of raising them in a family environment.*

Keywords: *Family environment, psychological support, physical development, mental health, individual education, inclusive education.*

NOGIRON BOLALI OILALARGA PEDAGOGIK VA PSIXOLOGIK YORDAM
KO'RSATISH

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotda nogiron bolali oilalarga pedagogik va psixologik yordam ko'rsatish bo'yicha ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan. Ushbu ma'lumotlarning asosiy qismi nogiron bolali oilalarga davlatimiz tomonidan ko'rsatiladigan yordamlar haqida aytib o'tiladi. Shuningdek tadqiqotimiz davomida nogironligi bo'lgan bolalarning, imkoniyatlari cheklagan bolalarning psixologik salomatligi, ularni oila muhitida tarbiyalashning asosiy jihatlari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Oilaviy muhit, psixologik yordam, jismoniy rivojlanish, ruxiy salomatlik, individual ta'lim, inklyuziv ta'lim.*

ОКАЗАНИЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ И ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДДЕРЖКИ
СЕМЬЯМ С ДЕТЬМИ-ИНВАЛИДАМИ

Аннотация. *В данном исследовании представлена информация об оказании педагогической и психологической поддержки семьям с детьми-инвалидами. Основная часть этой информации касается поддержки, оказываемой нашим государством семьям с детьми-инвалидами. Также в нашем исследовании представлена информация о психологическом здоровье детей с ограниченными возможностями, детей с ограниченными возможностями и основных аспектах их воспитания в семейной среде.*

Ключевые слова: Семейная среда, психологическая поддержка, физическое развитие, психическое здоровье, индивидуальное образование, инклюзивное образование.

Introduction

Children with disabilities require special support for their physical, mental and emotional needs. This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the psychological development of children with disabilities, effective strategies for supporting them and their role in the family and social environment. The impact of psychological approaches, educational systems and social support on children is examined in detail. This study highlights the factors necessary for the optimal development of children with disabilities and their full participation in society. Children with disabilities are one of the most vulnerable groups in society. Their psychological development and education require special approaches. This study examines the developmental characteristics of children with disabilities, the factors affecting them and effective support strategies. Our research also provides practical recommendations for a deeper understanding of the psychology of children with disabilities and for helping them. Information is provided on the psychological development of children with disabilities. Children with disabilities face various difficulties in their development. These difficulties may be related to their physical, mental, and emotional needs.

Although the basic principles of psychological development are the same for all children, children with disabilities require an additional approach and support in these processes. Physical development. Children with disabilities may face limitations in their physical development. These limitations may range from their mobility to their fine motor skills. Special therapies and exercise programs should be introduced for these children. Such approaches will help them feel independent. The state provides material, advisory and other assistance to families caring for children with disabilities, in short, comprehensive support for individuals with special needs. The articles of Chapter 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child” establish additional guarantees of the rights of children in need of social protection. The protection of the rights of persons with disabilities in the political, socio-economic and cultural spheres of society is based on the principle of non-discrimination against a person, including on the basis of disability, regardless of the situation. It is very important that not only state structures, but also civil society institutions are active in this regard. At the same time, there is a need to guarantee the rights of children with disabilities to a family environment. In this regard, support should also be provided to children in the care of persons with disabilities.

For example, a child living with a parent or other caregiver with disabilities should receive support that fully protects their rights and, if it is in their best interests, allows them to continue living with their parents. Support services should also include various forms of temporary care for the sick, such as home care or community-based day care. These services should help parents to work, reduce their workload and maintain a healthy family environment. The role of the family, which remains the basis of childcare in many communities and is considered one of the best alternatives to childcare, should be strengthened and support the child, his or her parents or other caregivers. While foster care is an accepted and widespread form of alternative care in many countries, many foster families are hesitant to care for a child with a disability, as they often assume that children with disabilities may cause problems or have special needs for additional care, physical, psychological, or intellectual development. Therefore, organizations responsible for placing children in foster care should provide the families concerned with the necessary training and encouragement and support them in providing appropriate care for the child with disabilities.

The United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child has expressed concern about the high number of children with disabilities placed in specialized children's institutions in many countries. The quality of services provided there, be it educational, medical or rehabilitation, often does not meet the requirements for the care of children with disabilities. This is due to the lack of established standards, their inconsistency, lack of compliance with them or insufficient supervision. Such institutions are vulnerable special environments where children with disabilities are more likely to be exposed to psychological, physical and other forms of violence, as well as neglect. In this regard, the Committee calls on States parties to use institutionalization only as a measure of last resort, in cases of extreme necessity and in the best interests of the child. It recommends that States parties put an end to the practice of placing children in institutions solely for the purpose of restricting the child's liberty or freedom of movement. In addition, attention should be paid to the reorganization of existing children's institutions, to giving priority to small residential facilities that fully respect the rights and needs of the child, and to the development of national standards for the quality of care in institutions. They should be monitored to ensure compliance with the rules and the effective implementation of the standards. With reference to paragraph 48 of the general recommendation, the Committee is concerned that the views of children with disabilities are rarely taken into account when separating them from their parents and placing them in institutions. In general, despite the long-term impact of these decisions on children's lives and futures, decision-making processes do not sufficiently consider children as full partners. In this regard, the Committee recommends that States parties continue and strengthen

their efforts to promote the participation of children with disabilities in all aspects of the process of integration and assessment, separation from parents and institutionalization, and during the transition period. The Committee also emphasizes that the views of children should be heard at all stages of the implementation of protective measures, before, during and after the decision-making process. In this regard, the Committee draws the attention of States parties to the recommendations adopted by the Committee on 16 September 2005 at its general day of discussion on children left without parental care. Therefore, when considering the issue of institutionalization of children, States parties are encouraged to develop programmes for the deinstitutionalization of children and their return to their families, foster care or foster care. Parents and other family members should be provided with the necessary and systematic support to facilitate the child's integration into the home environment. The education system and conditions for children with disabilities have been created. Special education settings are important for children with disabilities. These settings are designed to meet the individual needs of children and support their development. Special education programs, resource centers, and individualized education plans are key elements of education for children with disabilities. Individualized education plans. Individualized education plans are developed specifically for each child with disabilities. These plans include the child's learning needs, developmental goals, and support measures. Individualized education identifies all the resources and services that children need to succeed in their education. Family support services. Support services are essential for the education of children with disabilities. These services are provided by special education teachers, therapists, psychologists, and other professionals. Support services ensure that children succeed in their education. Social and psychological needs of children with disabilities. The social development of children with disabilities is important for their successful integration into society. Social development occurs through children's friendships, group activities and learning social rules. Special support and training are necessary for the social development of children with disabilities. Children with disabilities and the family environment. The family is the most important source of support for children with disabilities. The family's loving, understanding and patient approach plays a major role in the development of children. Family support develops children's self-esteem and social skills. The family environment should be safe and supportive for children with disabilities. Special equipment in the home, adapted learning environments and family activities support children's development. The family environment helps children feel free and secure.

Support programs and advice for parents contribute greatly to the development of children with disabilities. There are special trainings, counselling services and support groups for parents.

Conclusion

Many psychological problems can be overcome by creating a social inclusion education program. Social inclusion involves ensuring the full participation of children with disabilities in society. Social inclusion policies and programs are aimed at creating equal opportunities for children with disabilities and protecting their rights. These policies ensure justice and equity in society. The psychological development and education of children with disabilities require special approaches and support. This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the developmental characteristics of children with disabilities, effective strategies for helping them, and their role in the family and social environment. The impact of psychological approaches, educational systems, and social support on children is examined in detail.

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